

Effect of the Nature of Disperse Phase on the Extent of Vicinal Continuous Phase in Oil/Water Emulsions*

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The ratio of the co-sphere radius to the radius of the corresponding droplet for different oil/water/Na-oleate emulsions with benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-xylenes, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene as disperse phases were taken from the earlier works of the authors and compared. The effect of the nature of disperse phase on the extent of vicinal continuous phase was discussed in terms of the steric and the electrical effects of the substituent groups in the disperse phase molecules and of the solubility of the emulsifier in the disperse phase.

THE existence of a layer of considerable thickness of continuous phase surrounding the dispersed droplets in emulsion systems has been reported by earlier workers¹⁻³. Recently the authors in their earlier publications⁴⁻⁶ discussed the existence of a co-sphere of continuous phase enclosing each emulsified droplet in oil/water emulsions and calculated the ratio of the co-sphere radius to the radius of the corresponding emulsified droplet at varying emulsifier concentration for different uncreamed as well as creamed emulsions. The present communication is an attempt to explain the effect of the nature of disperse phase on the size of such co-spheres.

Discussion

In view of the above, the relevant data were taken from the earlier work of the authors^{5,6} and are included in Table 1 where ϕ_c is the value of the phase-volume ratio ϕ for which the co-spheres of average radius r_c in an uncreamed oil/water/Na-oleate emulsion with an average droplet radius r_d touch each other and r_{scream} is the average radius of the co-spheres when the droplets are closely packed in the creamed emulsion with cream thickness h_c .

From a close observation of the Table it is apparent that the order of ϕ_c values for the systems considered is *m*-xylene > *o*-xylene > toluene > benzene > chlorobenzene > bromobenzene > *p*-xylene.

Further, as r_s/r_d is determined by the equation⁴

$$r_s/r_d = (0.74/\phi_c)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (1)$$

the order for the same under similar condition is *p*-xylene > bromobenzene > chlorobenzene > benzene > toluene > *o*-xylene > *m*-xylene.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF ϕ_c , R_s/R_d AND (R_{scream}/R_d) ($h_c \phi \rightarrow 0$) FOR DIFFERENT IDENTICALLY PREPARED OIL/WATER/NA-OLEATE EMULSION SYSTEMS

Temp. = 30° ± 0.2°					
Sl. No.	Disperse phase	C*	ϕ_c	r_s/r_d	(r_{scream}/r_d) ($h_c \phi \rightarrow 0$)
1.	Benzene	1.0	0.430	1.198	1.012
		1.5	0.400	1.228	1.013
		2.0	0.376	1.253	1.016
2.	Toluene	1.0	0.444	1.186	1.012
		1.5	0.409	1.219	1.013
		2.0	0.381	1.248	1.015
3.	<i>o</i> -xylene	1.0	0.451	1.179	1.010
		1.5	0.415	1.213	1.012
		2.0	0.383	1.246	1.015
4.	<i>m</i> -xylene	1.0	0.464	1.168	1.010
		1.5	0.416	1.212	1.012
		2.0	0.390	1.238	1.013
5.	<i>p</i> -xylene	1.0	0.385	1.243	1.013
		1.5	0.365	1.266	1.015
		2.0	0.358	1.274	1.016
6.	Cl-benzene	1.0	0.398	1.230	—
		1.5	0.378	1.251	—
		2.0	0.374	1.255	—
7.	Br-benzene	1.0	0.390	1.238	—
		1.5	0.376	1.253	—
		2.0	0.373	1.257	—

*C=Concentration of Na-oleate as emulsifier in gms per 100 ml of emulsion.

In order to explain the effect on ϕ_c of the substituents introduced in the benzene ring we can write

$$\Delta\phi_c = (\delta\phi_c)_E + (\delta\phi_c)_S + (\delta\phi_c)_L \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\phi_c$ is the difference in ϕ_c value of a substituted benzene and that of benzene, while $(\delta\phi_c)_E$ and $(\delta\phi_c)_S$ are the contributions of the electrical and steric effects

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of the substituents and $(\delta\phi_o)_L$ is the contribution of the emulsifier solubility in the substituted benzene as disperse phase.

Since the solubility of Na-oleate as emulsifier in the substituted benzenes as disperse phase in the systems considered is negligible, the variation in $(\delta\phi_o)_L$ at constant emulsifier concentration for identically prepared emulsions may be taken as insignificant. Further, as the obvious steric effect of the substituent group is to check the folding up of emulsifier chains leading to increased co-sphere, $(\delta\phi_o)_S$ will always remain negative ; whereas $(\delta\phi_o)_E$ may be positive or negative depending on whether the electrical effect of the substituent group leads to increased or decreased surface charge density in comparison to that of an emulsion system with benzene as disperse phase.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF SIGN OF $\Delta\phi_o$ AND CHARGE ON THE SUBSTITUENT GROUP OF DISPERSE PHASE

Sl No.	Disperse phase	Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$			Nature of charge on substituent group
		$C=1.0\%$	$C=1.5\%$	$C=2.0\%$	
1.	Toluene	0.014	0.009	0.005	+ve
2.	<i>o</i> -xylene	0.021	0.015	0.007	+ve
3.	<i>m</i> -xylene	0.034	0.016	0.014	+ve
4.	Cl-benzene	-0.032	-0.022	-0.002	-ve
5.	Br-benzene	-0.040	-0.024	-0.003	-ve
6.	<i>p</i> -xylene	-0.045	-0.035	-0.018	+ve

Thus from Table 2 it can be seen that for the disperse phases in serial nos. 1, 2 and 3 the charge on the substituent group as well as the corresponding sign of $\Delta\phi_o$ is positive. This suggests that for these systems with sodium oleate as emulsifier which gives negative charge to the emulsified droplets, $(\delta\phi_o)_E$ is positive and $|(\delta\phi_o)_E| > |(\delta\phi_o)_S|$. For the disperse phases in serial nos. 4 and 5, the nature of the charge on the substituent

group and the corresponding sign of $\Delta\phi_o$ both are negative signifying that $(\delta\phi_o)_E$ is negative and both the electrical and steric effects of the substituent aid each other. On the other hand, for the disperse phase in serial no. 6 while the charge on the substituent group is positive, the corresponding $\Delta\phi_o$ is negative. This indicates that $(\delta\phi_o)_E$ is positive but $|(\delta\phi_o)_E| < |(\delta\phi_o)_S|$.

Since the nature of the contributions of substituents towards $\Delta\phi_o$ in creamed emulsions remain the same as those in the uncreamed emulsions, the apparent deviations in the order of $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_a)$ ($h_o\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$ as compared to that of r_s/r_a do not seem to warrant any drastic change in the expected trend. In each case the value of r_s/r_a is greater than that of $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_a)$ ($h_o\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$ for the same emulsion system and while the former is a measure of the maximum, the latter is a measure of the minimum amount of the modified vicinal continuous phase per droplet.

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References

1. J. O. SIBREE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 26 ; 1931, 27, 161.
2. B. A. TOMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 542.
3. P. SHERMAN, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, (London), 1950, 69, Suppl. No. 2, S 70.
4. R. P. SINGH and S. S. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 125.
5. R. P. SINGH and S. S. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 113.
6. R. P. SINGH and S. S. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 398.